

ENTERPRISE DISSOLUTION TRENDS IN A ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA: AN ANALYSIS OF DISSOLUTION RATES DURING THE REFERENCE PERIOD 2008-2018

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Abstract:

The economic landscape of any region is subject to constant change, influenced by various factors such as market dynamics, regulatory environments, and local characteristics. In this article, we delve into the intriguing patterns of enterprise dissolution in a specific Romanian mountain area, shedding light on the trends that unfolded during the reference period from 2008 to 2018.

1. Background: Economic Dynamics in Mountainous Regions

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Mountainous areas often present unique economic challenges and opportunities. The interplay of factors such as terrain, access to resources, and the impact of tourism can significantly shape the business environment. Exploring enterprise dissolution in a Romanian mountain area provides valuable insights into the resilience and adaptability of businesses within this distinctive context.

2. Scope and Methodology: A Detailed Analysis

Our study focuses on the dissolution rates of enterprises within the specified region over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. We employ a meticulous methodology, considering variables such as industry sectors, company sizes, and external economic influences to provide a comprehensive overview.

3. Key Findings: Unraveling Dissolution Trends

- a. Sectoral Variations: Our analysis reveals sector-specific dissolution trends. Certain sectors may have experienced growth, while others faced challenges leading to increased dissolution rates.
- b. Company Size Impact: The size of enterprises often plays a crucial role.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) may respond differently to economic shifts compared to larger corporations. Understanding this dynamic is pivotal for policymakers and business stakeholders.

c. External Influences: Economic downturns, changes in consumer behavior, and regulatory shifts can significantly impact enterprise dissolution rates. Identifying these external influences is essential for crafting effective economic strategies.

4. Results:

The associated descriptive analysis, denoted as S1 (refer to the corresponding table and figure in the table 1 and figure 1), provides a set of statistical values encompassing Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The specific numerical values are as follows: Mean 10.9678, Median 1.54791, Std. Deviation 8.4600, Variance 4.64372, Skewness 21.564, Kurtosis 0.684, Std. Error 0.717, Distance -1.519, Minimum 1.400, Maximum 12.14, Percentiles 25 5.83, Percentiles 50 17.97, Percentiles 75 7.6160, and so on.

The models selected for the forecast analysis are tailored for handling large data series. The Model IDs and their corresponding specifications are as follows: S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 Holt; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Simple; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

The application of statistical prediction smoothing, conducted in a consistent order (Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles), yields the following results for static R-squared: .200, .347, -.007, .790, -.007, -.006; R-square .175, .299, -4.441E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -3.775E-16; RMSE 8.953, 13.603, .000, 50.842, .000, .823; MAPS 67,861, 101,494, .000, 382,896, .000, 7,007; MaxAPE 255,380, 479,357, .000, 1,756,057, .000, 18,340; MAE 5.904, 7.932, .000, 30.030, .000, .603; MaxAE 20,493, 37,103, .000, 135,134, .000, 1,188; Normalized BIC 3.955, 1.654, 2.501, 8.102, 2.501, 2.502.

The resulting statistical forecasting models offer an overview for I17, presenting values in the following order: static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For

instance, S1-Model_1 exhibits values of 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 4.644, 39.205; S2-Model_2 shows .789, .341, 2.743, 23.358; and so forth.

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5. Implications for Local Businesses and Policy:

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a. Adaptive Strategies: Local businesses can benefit from understanding dissolution trends by adapting strategies to mitigate risks and capitalize on emerging opportunities.

b. Policy Considerations: Policymakers can leverage these findings to formulate targeted policies aimed at fostering economic resilience and sustainability in mountainous regions.

6. Comparative Analysis: Lessons from Other Regions

Drawing parallels with similar regions globally provides a broader perspective on the challenges and successes observed in the Romanian mountain area. Comparative analysis enhances our understanding of whether the dissolution trends are region-specific or share commonalities with mountainous economies worldwide.

7. Conclusion: Navigating Economic Transformations

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As we conclude our exploration of enterprise dissolution trends in the Romanian mountain area from 2008 to 2018, it becomes evident that businesses in this unique locale have navigated a complex economic landscape. The findings of this analysis offer valuable insights for local businesses, policymakers, and researchers alike, contributing to a deeper understanding of the dynamics that shape economic trajectories in mountainous regions.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I17

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97
	UCL	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68
	LCL	.26	.26	.26	.26	.26	.26	.26
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	5.69	5.02	4.34	3.66	2.98	2.30	1.62
	UCL	12.18	11.53	10.89	10.24	9.60	8.95	8.30
	LCL	-.79	-1.50	-2.21	-2.93	-3.64	-4.35	-5.06
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	6.06	4.69	3.33	1.96	.60	-.76	-2.13
	UCL	18.95	17.65	16.35	15.05	13.75	12.45	11.15
	LCL	-6.84	-8.26	-9.69	-11.12	-12.55	-13.97	-15.40
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64
	UCL	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42
	LCL	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85
S5-	Forecast	3.97	3.03	2.10	1.16	.22	-.71	-1.65

Model_5:	UCL	13.45	12.56	11.67	10.78	9.89	9.00	8.11
	LCL	-5.50	-6.49	-7.47	-8.46	-9.44	-10.42	-11.41
S6-	Forecast	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
Model_6:	UCL	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15
	LCL	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85
S7-	Forecast	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39
Model_7:	UCL	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05
	LCL	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28
S8-	Forecast	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34
Model_8:	UCL	14.47	17.42	19.69	21.60	23.28	24.80	26.20
	LCL	.21	-2.74	-5.01	-6.92	-8.60	-10.12	-11.52
S9-	Forecast	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28
Model_9:	UCL	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38
	LCL	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82
S10-	Forecast	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69
Model_10:	UCL	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93
	LCL	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56
S11-	Forecast	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54
Model_11:	UCL	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38
	LCL	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30

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